

Fire Monitoring and Air Quality Analysis in Egypt Using Satellite Data

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Project Summary:

This ambitious project aims to leverage the latest technologies in remote sensing to monitor and analyze fires and their resulting emissions in the Arab Republic of Egypt, reflecting a profound concern for environmental issues and sustainable development. Fires represent one of the major challenges facing the Egyptian environment, causing destruction to forests and natural resources, as well as negatively impacting air quality and public health.

The project will accurately address the environmental impact of fires by analyzing precise data extracted from advanced satellites such as Sentinel, Landsat, and MODIS. A scientific methodology will be implemented that includes data collection and analysis using advanced techniques, providing a comprehensive and accurate view of fire conditions across the country. This data will be used to identify fire hotspots, track their spread, and analyze the potential impacts on various ecosystems, including changes in biomass and vegetation.

Additionally, the project will develop a comprehensive computational program aimed at estimating fines resulting from harmful human activities in various sectors such as factories, farms, workshops, and waste collection sites. This program will rely on an advanced mathematical model that analyzes various parameters, such as the type of activity, pollutant type, emission volume, and geographical location, enabling authorities to make data-driven decisions. This program will contribute to enhancing environmental protection efforts by implementing strict policies based on accurate data, leading to reduced negative impacts of pollution and improved compliance with environmental laws.

Furthermore, the project will work to raise environmental awareness among various segments of society through awareness and education campaigns aimed at clarifying the importance of environmental conservation and the impact of fires on public health. The local community, including schools and cultural centers, will be engaged to enhance community participation in environmental protection efforts.

This project is not limited to monitoring and analysis; it also seeks to achieve a tangible positive impact on environmental policies by providing data-driven recommendations that contribute to improving environmental legislation and enhancing the protection of natural resources. Through this work, we aspire to create a sustainable and healthy future for generations to come, strengthening the role of the Arab Republic of Egypt as a model for environmental protection and compliance with international standards.

Objectives:

1. Enhancing National Security:

This project aims to contribute to maintaining the state's national security by using remote sensing technologies to monitor fires and their emissions. Relevant authorities will cooperate with the Egyptian Armed Forces and the Ministry of Interior to exchange

vital information and accurate data, enhancing the state's capacity to deal with natural disasters and ensure citizens' safety.

2. **Activating Security Response:**
Work to improve the mechanisms for rapid response by the Armed Forces and the Ministry of Interior when fires or natural disasters occur. Geographic information systems will be developed to provide accurate real-time data to support relief and rescue operations, enhancing coordination between various security and civil agencies.
3. **Monitoring and Tracking Fires:**
Utilizing advanced satellite data to accurately and in real-time monitor fire locations throughout Egypt. Spectral analysis and artificial intelligence techniques will be applied to improve fire detection accuracy and determine the extent of their spread, enabling faster and more effective responses (Vikram, 2018).
4. **Analyzing Smoke and Emissions:**
Conducting comprehensive studies to assess the impact of smoke and emissions resulting from fires on air quality and local climate. Atmospheric simulation models will be used to study short-term and long-term effects on human health and ecosystems, including estimating health and environmental damage costs (Zain, 2019).
5. **Environmental Preservation:**
Effectively contributing to the protection of forests and agricultural crops while reducing the damage caused by fires to the environment. By studying the impacts of fires on biodiversity, we aim to promote sustainability and preserve natural resources for future generations.
6. **Increasing Awareness:**
Raising public awareness about the necessity of protection against forest fires and their harmful effects on health and the environment. We will organize workshops and awareness campaigns that include the use of social media and community engagement to raise awareness about the importance of environmental conservation and the risks of fires (Al-Husseini, 2023).
7. **Developing a Computational Program:**
Creating an advanced computational program to calculate fines resulting from environmental pollution caused by human activities. The program will rely on comprehensive data models to assess potential financial penalties, helping to enforce sanctions and promote compliance with environmental laws.
8. **Environmental Impact Assessment:**
Using data extracted from satellites to assess the impact of fires on the environment, including analyzing land use changes and assessing the effects on wildlife and ecosystems (Raji, 2020). This will contribute to providing data-driven recommendations for improving environmental protection policies.
9. **Enhancing Cooperation Between Security Agencies:**
Working to enhance cooperation between the Egyptian Armed Forces and the Ministry of Interior in confronting forest fires and exchanging information related to environmental security. This cooperation will help implement comprehensive strategies to address security challenges arising from fires.
10. **Improving Environmental Policies:**
Providing data-driven recommendations to policymakers for improving environmental

policies and effectively addressing fires, contributing to the enhancement of laws and regulations related to environmental protection.

11. Enhancing International Cooperation:

Building partnerships with international and local organizations specializing in remote sensing and disaster management, enhancing the exchange of knowledge and experiences, and increasing the effectiveness of fire combat strategies at the regional and international levels.

Target Audience:

1. Government Entities:

- **Civil Protection:** Accurate and updated data will be provided to assist civil protection teams in making quick and effective decisions during fires, facilitating their implementation of emergency plans and immediate response strategies. This data will also enhance the training and ongoing development of personnel in this field.
- **Ministry of Environment:** The ministry will benefit from the results of the analyzed data to develop effective environmental policies contributing to environmental protection. Results can also be used to identify areas most prone to fires and develop appropriate protection plans.

2. Local and International Environmental Organizations:

These organizations will contribute to expanding the project by providing technical and financial support. They will also use the information generated by the project in their awareness campaigns and environmental research, enhancing their efforts to protect the environment and mitigate the effects of climate change.

3. Researchers and Academics:

Researchers and universities will benefit from the large data sets to be collected and analyzed, providing opportunities for in-depth academic studies. These studies may lead to the publication of leading scientific research contributing to the development of new technologies in remote sensing and environmental data analysis.

4. General Public:

The project will enhance environmental awareness among the public by organizing interactive workshops and awareness campaigns. Social media and community initiatives will be used to educate individuals about the risks associated with fires and how to manage them. The goal is to empower the community to be part of the efforts to protect the environment.

5. Private Sector:

The private sector, especially companies operating in agriculture, waste management, and renewable energy, can benefit from the information provided by the project. This will enable them to develop more sustainable strategies and comply with environmental laws.

6. Educational Institutions:

The findings and lessons learned from the project will be integrated into curricula to educate students about the importance of environmental conservation and the use of technology in disaster management. These initiatives will help motivate the next generation to care about environmental issues.

7. **International Partners:**

This includes international organizations focusing on environmental and climate issues, such as the United Nations and the United Nations Environment Programme. These partners will be able to use the available data to develop integrated strategies to address the challenges of fires and emissions at both regional and international levels.

Project Content:

Fires are natural phenomena that pose a significant threat to the environment, contributing to the destruction of forests and biodiversity, and negatively impacting air quality and human health. In recent years, Egypt has witnessed a noticeable increase in the frequency of fires due to human activities, such as unsustainable agriculture and deforestation, along with the effects of climate change, which exacerbate these phenomena (Zain, 2019). Thus, monitoring fires and analyzing their resulting emissions becomes a priority that should be given special attention to protect the environment and public health.

The proposed project relies on the use of remote sensing technologies, benefiting from advanced satellite data such as Sentinel and Landsat. The goal is to monitor fires accurately and estimate their environmental impacts effectively, enhancing the capacity to make informed decisions to mitigate environmental risks.

Research Methodology:

- **Data Collection:** Satellite data will be used to monitor fires and their resulting emissions. This includes obtaining images of specific areas and determining when the fires occurred.
- **Data Analysis:** Geographic analysis techniques and environmental models will be applied to assess the environmental impact of fires on affected areas, providing accurate insights into the extent of losses and various effects (Vikram, 2018).
- **Developing a Computational Program:** An advanced algorithm will be created using the Python programming language to estimate fines resulting from polluting activities, contributing to the development of effective environmental policies.

Computational Program for Calculating Fines:

To estimate fines related to environmental pollution resulting from human activities, a program has been developed that includes the following criteria:

- **Type of Activity:** Determining whether the activity occurs in a factory, farm, workshop, or waste collection site, helping to better understand the pollution source.
- **Type of Pollutants:** Classifying pollutants into air, water, or solid waste, reflecting the impact of each type on the environment.
- **Volume of Emissions:** Measuring emissions in kilograms or tons to estimate the pollution resulting from each activity.
- **Geographical Location:** Considering the proximity of the location to environmentally or population-sensitive areas, increasing the significance of impact estimation.
- **Health Damages:** Assessing the number of affected individuals or areas impacted by pollution, reflecting the social and psychological consequences of polluting activities.

Number of Images Captured of Egypt by Satellites

Egypt is an important geographical area regarding the use of satellites for Earth observation, as the availability of multiple satellites allows for the collection of a large number of images from various regions. Below are some details about different satellites and how they monitor Egypt:

1. Landsat:

- **Number of images captured of Egypt per day:** Landsat satellites (such as Landsat 8) can capture approximately one image for each location on Earth every 16 days. With several satellites in the program, the revisit rate can be improved in certain areas (Ragi, 2020).

2. Sentinel-2:

- **Number of images captured of Egypt per day:** Each satellite in the Sentinel-2 series can capture images every 5 days for each location. With two satellites (Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B) in orbit, a revisit rate of up to two days can be achieved for full coverage of Egypt (Zain, 2019).

3. MODIS:

- **Number of images captured of Egypt per day:** MODIS satellites capture images twice daily (one in the morning and one in the evening), resulting in approximately 2 images per day that cover Egypt completely (Vikram, 2018).

4. WorldView:

- **Number of images captured of Egypt per day:** WorldView satellites (such as WorldView-3) can capture about 1-20 images per day, depending on specific imaging locations and demand. In general, they can cover Egypt multiple times a day (Zain, 2019).

5. PlanetScope:

- **Number of images captured of Egypt per day:** PlanetScope satellites can capture about 3-5 images daily for each area, providing good coverage of Egypt throughout the week (Ragi, 2020).

Conclusion

Based on the mentioned systems, the total number of images captured of Egypt can exceed 10 images daily from various satellites. The frequency of available images depends on the type of satellite, the targeted area, and weather conditions. This figure is estimated and may vary based on different circumstances, necessitating precise and continuous data management to maximize the utility of available environmental information.

Expected Results:

- Providing accurate data on fire locations and emissions.
- Estimating the environmental impact of fires on public health and the environment (Hosseini, 2023).
- Developing tools for environmental monitoring and enhancing compliance with environmental laws.

Discussion:

Studying the impact of fires on the environment is a critical area that requires increasing attention, especially given the challenges posed by climate change and human activities. In Egypt, fires caused by agricultural and industrial activities are significant factors negatively affecting the environment and public health.

Research has shown that fires emit large amounts of greenhouse gases, contributing to the worsening of global warming (Chuvieco et al., 2019). This highlights the importance of using remote sensing technologies, which allow for real-time monitoring of fires and a more accurate assessment of environmental impacts, thereby helping to improve fire management strategies.

It is essential that any future policies or strategies are based on reliable and accurate data. Without such data, it will be difficult to identify patterns and trends related to fires, making the proposed project a crucial step toward achieving that goal.

References:

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